

A sorter for electrons based on magnetic elements

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Abstract

The orbital angular momentum (OAM) sorter is an electron optical device for the measurement of an electron's OAM. It is based on two phase elements, which are referred to as an “unwrapper” and a “corrector” and are located in Fourier conjugate planes. The simplest implementation of the sorter is based on the use of electrostatic phase elements, such as a charged needle for the unwrapper and electrodes with alternating charges or potentials for the corrector. Here, we use a formal analogy between phase shifts introduced by charges and vertical currents to propose alternative designs for the sorter elements, which are based on phase shifts introduced by magnetic fields. We use this concept to provide a general guide for phase element design, which promises to provide improved reliability of phase control in electron optics.

Keywords: Electron vortex beam, magnetic phase plate, electron optics, electron orbital angular momentum, sorter.

1. Introduction

A key strength of transmission electron microscopy is its ability to make use of information from both diffraction space and real space through the smart use of electron optics [1]. However, not long after the introduction of techniques such as electron magnetic circular dichroism [2], it became clear that electron microscopy requires a technique that can be used to measure an electron's orbital angular momentum (OAM) [3], which is neither a real space nor a diffraction space property. OAM is a quantum vectorial operator, whose component along the average propagation direction for a paraxial beam can be written in position representation as the azimuthal derivative of the wave. Its eigenstates are the now well-known vortex beams, whose phase winds in the azimuthal direction [4, 5, 6, 7].

The introduction of electron vortex beams triggered developments in physics that include new measurement tools [8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. Whereas the generation of OAM eigenstates is relatively simple, their measurement and decomposition has proved to be more cumbersome. In particular, methods that have been used to measure OAM composition [13, 14, 15, 16]

typically suffer from an inability to cleanly separate the radial and angular degrees of freedom of the electron beam [17].

A new device, which is referred to as an ‘‘OAM sorter’’, promises to overcome this problem by introducing a conformal transformation from Cartesian to polar coordinates to separate different OAM components [18, 19, 20, 21]. The realization and application of this device is an active topic in electron optics. It has been realized using both holographic[19] and electrostatic elements[22], based on theoretical concepts[20, 21]. However, its implementation is still not straightforward as a result of practical problems. When using electrostatic elements, a needle-shaped electrode is typically used to perform the transformation, while a periodic array of alternatively-charged electrodes in the corresponding diffraction plane is used to correct the transformation phase. When using holograms, similar phase distributions can be imprinted directly in the form of thickness modulations of the diffraction gratings. In the long term, a needle can become contaminated as a result of exposure to the electron beam, resulting in a change in its electrostatic field, whereas charging and wear can affect a grating material. In addition, the shape of a needle needs to be controlled accurately. Whereas a line of constant charge should be placed in the path of the electron beam, the device is in practice based on the use of conductive electrodes that can only be used to control potentials. A further problem in the electrostatic device results from a chromatic effect on the phase.

It is well known that magnetic lenses are less problematic than electrostatic lenses. Here, we introduce the concept of using magnetic fields as phase elements in the sorter by building on a formal analogy between the phase imparted to an electron beam by a charge and a vertical current. This analogy, which has been suggested in recent experimental work [23, 24], is presented systematically in the first section of this paper, in order to demonstrate that the effects of electrostatic phase elements can be reproduced by using either currents or permanent magnets. Key advantages of using a current are that it is more stable than a charge distribution, it can be controlled directly and its (magnetic) effect on the phase is independent of incident electron energy. After a short description of the operation of an ideal sorter device, we introduce new configurations of sorter elements that are based on currents and magnets. Just as for the electrostatic case, we discuss additional corrections that are required to remove residual astigmatism and we assess the experimental feasibility of the concept.

2. The ideal sorter

We begin by recalling, for the sake of completeness, the basic equations that describe an ideal sorter, first developed for light optics. The key component of the optical sorter transforms azimuthal position in the input beam into linear transverse position in the output beam, which is located in the Fraunhofer diffraction plane of the input beam. An input image comprising concentric circles is then transformed into an output image of parallel lines. However, this transformation introduces a phase distortion that needs to be corrected by a second element. The complete system then comprises two optical elements, with the first element transforming the image and the second element correcting for phase distortions introduced by the first element. The second element is positioned in the Fourier plane of the first element, which can be achieved by using a Fourier-transforming lens of focal length f [18].

The phase profile of the transforming optical element, which is referred to as an ‘‘unwrapper’’ or ‘‘sorter 1’’, is given by the expression

$$\phi_1(x, y) = \frac{d}{\lambda f} \left[y \arctan(x, y) - x \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{b} \right) + x \right], \quad (1)$$

which performs the conformal mapping $(x, y) \rightarrow (u, v)$ to its Fourier plane (u, v) , with

$$u = -\frac{d}{2\pi} \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{b} \right) \quad (2)$$

and

$$v = \frac{d}{2\pi} \arctan(x, y). \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 1, λ is the wavelength of the incident electron beam. The parameter d is the length of the transformed beam, while b translates the transformed image in the u direction and can be chosen independently of d [18]. The function $\arctan(x, y)$ refers to the arc tangent of y/x , taking into account which quadrant the point (x, y) is in. The transforming optical element contains a half-line of discontinuity along the negative x axis, which defines the axis around which the OAM is measured and whose end corresponds to both the origin of the coordinate system and the location of the tip (see below).

The second optical element, which is referred to as the ‘‘corrector’’ or ‘‘sorter 2’’, introduces a phase correction of the form

$$\phi_2(u, v) = -\frac{db}{\lambda f} \exp \left(-2\pi \frac{u}{d} \right) \cos \left(2\pi \frac{v}{d} \right). \quad (4)$$

By adding a second Fourier transforming lens of focal length F after the phase correcting element, OAM states can be separated in its focal plane.

When using refractive elements instead of diffractive spatial light modulators, in order to have an efficient and compact mode transformer [25] it has been found to be convenient to add to ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 a thin convergent spherical lens of focal length f equal to the distance between the two elements, with the transmission function

$$\psi_f(x, y) = \exp \left[\frac{-i\pi(x^2 + y^2)}{\lambda f} \right]. \quad (5)$$

3. Sorter elements based on currents

Whereas a phase shift can be introduced by a local variation in refractive index and relative optical distance in visible light optics, it is related to electromagnetic potentials in electron optics. According to the standard high energy phase object approximation [26], the electron optical phase shift $\varphi(x, y)$ can be written in the form

$$\varphi(x, y) = C_E \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} V(x, y, z) dz - \frac{2\pi e}{h} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A_z(x, y, z) dz, \quad (6)$$

where $C_E = \frac{2\pi e}{\lambda E} \frac{E_0 + E}{2E_0 + E}$, e is the absolute value of the electron charge, h is Planck’s constant, λ is the de Broglie electron wavelength, E is the electron’s energy, E_0 is the electron’s rest mass energy and $A_z(x, y, z)$ is the z component of the magnetic vector potential. The z axis of the coordinate system is aligned to the optical axis of the transmission electron microscope and has the same direction as the incident electron beam.

The equations that link V and A_z to their sources can be reduced to an identical form by noticing that (in the Coulomb Gauge)

$$\nabla^2 V = \frac{-\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\nabla^2 A_z = \mu_0 j_z , \quad (8)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum permeability and the charge density ρ plays the same role as j_z , which describes the component of the current density parallel to the main propagation direction of the electron beam. According to these expressions, in-plane components of the current density do not contribute to the phase shift. They can eventually produce small, point-dependent wave translations, which can be neglected in most cases [23]. Taken together, the three equations show that, in the phase object approximation, the phase shift is proportional to the z integral of the potentials. The equation for the phase shift can then be written in the form [27]

$$\nabla_{\perp}^2 \varphi = \frac{-C_E \sigma}{\epsilon_0} - \frac{2\pi e}{h} \mu_0 \zeta , \quad (9)$$

where $\sigma = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \rho dz$ and $\zeta = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} j_z dz$.

In this approximation, an inclined current in the plane x, z is equivalent to a vertical current j_z . A device that is used to control the phase using a charge distribution can therefore be reproduced by a series of vertical currents. This analogy is particularly relevant because it is often not the charge distribution but the equipotential distribution that can be controlled experimentally. Mathematically, the problem of finding appropriate boundary conditions for the potential in three dimensions can be transformed to the easier problem of finding projected sources of field in two dimensions. This difference is important when making conformal transformations of the electron wavefunction using harmonic phase elements, as suggested in the recent work of Ruffato *et al.* [28].

Here, we use this analogy to propose new alternative OAM sorter phase elements, which are based on magnetostatic phase shifts. Their design is obtained simply by substituting charges by vertical currents, or by equivalent Ampere currents for magnetic materials.

3.1. Unwrapper or sorter 1

We begin by considering a closed circuit carrying the current I between the tip of the device at $O=(0, 0, 0)$ and the points $A=(0, a, 0)$ and $B=(0, a, c)$, as shown in Fig. 1.

In order to calculate the phase shift due to a straight section of the current-carrying wire at position $\mathbf{r}_P = (x_P, y_P, z_P)$ directed along $d\mathbf{l} = (dx_P, dy_P, dz_P)$ and, more generally, of a closed loop, we make use of the fifth formulation of Ampere's law in terms of the vector potential, according to the expression [29]:

$$\mathbf{A}_z(x, y, z) = -\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} I \oint \frac{1}{r} d\mathbf{l} , \quad (10)$$

where $r = \sqrt{(x - x_P)^2 + (y - y_P)^2 + (z - z_P)^2}$ and $d\mathbf{l} = (dx_P, dy_P, dz_P)$.

As the phase shift described by Eq. 6 depends only on the z component of the vector potential, horizontal components of the wire can be neglected. It is convenient to parametrize the vertical segment OA in the form $\mathbf{r}_P = (0, a, c s)$, where $0 < s < 1$ and $d\mathbf{l} = (0, 0, c ds)$. Similarly, the oblique segment BO can be written $\mathbf{r}_P = (0, a s, c s)$, where $d\mathbf{l} = (0, -a, -c)ds$. The sum of the contributions of the two elements to the z component of the vector potential is therefore

$$d\mathbf{A}_z(x, y, z) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} I c ds \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{(x)^2 + (y - a)^2 + (z - c s)^2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{(x)^2 + (y - s a)^2 + (z - c s)^2}} \right] . \quad (11)$$

Making use of Eq. 6, we find for the contribution to the phase shift

$$d\varphi(x, y) = \frac{e \mu_0}{2 h} I c ds \{ \log(x^2 + (y - a)^2) - \log(x^2 + (y - a - s)^2) \} . \quad (12)$$

The total phase shift is then obtained by integrating the above expression in ds between 0 and 1, resulting in the expression

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{c e \mu_0 I}{2 a h} (y \log((a - y)^2 + x^2) + 2x \arctan\left(\frac{y-a}{x}\right) + 2a - y \log(x^2 + y^2) - 2x \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right)) . \quad (13)$$

In the limit of large a , we can make the approximations

$$y \log((a - y)^2 + x^2) - y \log(x^2 + y^2) \simeq -y \log\left(\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2}\right) \quad (14)$$

and

$$2x \arctan\left(\frac{y-a}{x}\right) - 2x \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) \simeq -2x \text{Sign}[a] \arctan[-\text{Sign}[a] y, x] , \quad (15)$$

where $\text{Sign}[x]$ is the sign function, so that

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{c e \mu_0 I}{2 a h} \left(-2x \text{Sign}[a] \arctan[-\text{Sign}[a] y, x] - y \log\left(\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2}\right) \right) . \quad (16)$$

If constant and linear terms are neglected, then the functional phase shift of the ideal sorter described by Eq. 1 is recovered, once it is noted that the discontinuity is aligned along the y axis and lies on the positive or negative side depending on the sign of a . The result is identical to that obtained in the electrostatic case [21] if the charge distribution is substituted by the current according to the analogy described above, provided that

$$\frac{d}{\lambda f} = 2 C_E C_V = \frac{c e \mu_0 I}{a h} , \quad (17)$$

where $C_V = \frac{K}{4\pi\epsilon_0}$, K is the constant charge density of a charged line and ϵ_0 is the dielectric constant of vacuum.

3.2. Corrector or sorter 2

In this case, we consider two current distributions that have the shapes of a square wave and a sinusoid, as sketched in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 3, respectively.

3.2.1. Square wave

A square wave current is equivalent to a periodic array of vertical wires at positions $(0, n d/2)$ carrying alternatively opposite currents, as the horizontal sections of the wire do not contribute to the phase. The phase shift of a single vertical wire of length $2L$ carrying current I at the origin [23] can be obtained from the first term of Eq. 12 with $a = 0$, in the form

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{e \mu_0}{h} IL \log[x^2 + y^2] . \quad (18)$$

Although it is a simple matter of addition to construct a finite square wave, it is more interesting to consider an infinite periodic arrangement of vertical wires at positions $(0, n d/2)$,

which can be described by the expression

$$\sum (-1)^n \frac{e \mu_0}{h} I L \log \left[(x - n \frac{d}{2})^2 + y^2 \right] . \quad (19)$$

As shown elsewhere, *e.g.*, in [30], this sum can be expressed analytically as

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{e \mu_0}{2h} I L \log \left(\frac{\cosh \left(\frac{2\pi y}{d} \right) - \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{d} \right)}{\cosh \left(\frac{2\pi y}{d} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{d} \right)} \right) . \quad (20)$$

For $y \gg d$, the leading term in this Fourier series reads

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{2 e \mu_0}{h} I L \exp \left(-\frac{2\pi|y|}{d} \right) \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{d} \right) . \quad (21)$$

Apart from a multiplying constant, this expression is coincident with the required functional form for sorter 2 described by Eq. 4. A cosine phase map of such an array is shown in Fig. 2(b).

3.2.2. Sinusoid

We describe a sinusoidal current by the parametric equation

$$\mathbf{r}_P = \left(x, 0, L \sin \left(\frac{2\pi x}{d} \right) \right) , \quad (22)$$

with

$$d\mathbf{l} = \left(1, 0, L \frac{2\pi}{c} \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{d} \right) \right) dx . \quad (23)$$

Even if the current is continuous, its z component varies as a cosine and it is equivalent to a cosine distribution of charges, resulting in the ability to generate the sorter phase explicitly without the need for approximations. The phase shift is then given by the expression

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{2e\mu_0}{h} IL \exp \left(-\frac{2\pi|y|}{d} \right) \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{d} \right) . \quad (24)$$

The current and corresponding phase shift are shown in Fig. 3.

4. Sorter elements based on magnetic materials

4.1. Unwrapper or sorter 1

The magnetic effect of a current in the phase shift can be obtained equivalently from a magnetized element. The analogy is obtained by shaping the edge of the magnetized element based on the current distribution. We begin by considering a magnetic lamina of small thickness t with vertices at the points $O=(0, 0, 0)$, $A=(0, a, 0)$ and $B=(0, a, c)$ and with a magnetization vector \mathbf{M} in the x direction, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{M} = (M, 0, 0)$, as shown in Fig. 4. The magnetic vector potential of an elementary magnetic dipole with moment $\mathbf{m} = (m, 0, 0) = (M t dy dz, 0, 0)$, located at the origin of the coordinate system, is given by the expression[29]

$$A_z = \left\{ 0, -\frac{\mu_0 m z}{4\pi (x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^{3/2}}, \frac{\mu_0 m y}{4\pi (x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^{3/2}} \right\} , \quad (25)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum permeability.

In the phase object approximation described by Eq. 6, the corresponding electron optical phase shift takes the form

$$\varphi(x, y) = -\frac{e \mu_0 m y}{h(x^2 + y^2)}. \quad (26)$$

As the phase shift does not depend on z , the contribution to the phase shift at the point (x, y) due to a column of dipoles at $(0, y_0, 0)$ of height $y_0 c/a$ (Fig. 4) is given by the expression

$$d\varphi(x, y) = -\frac{c e \mu_0 M t y_0(y - y_0)}{a h(x^2 + (y - y_0)^2)} dy_0. \quad (27)$$

By integrating the above equation from 0 to a , the phase shift associated with the triangular magnetic lamina turns out to be

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{c e \mu_0 M t}{2 a h} (y \log((a - y)^2 + x^2) + 2x \arctan\left(\frac{y-a}{x}\right) + 2a - y \log(x^2 + y^2) - 2x \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right)). \quad (28)$$

By making use of the same approximations as in Eq. 15 and Eq. 14, we obtain the expression

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{c e \mu_0 M t}{2 a h} \left(-2x \text{Sign}[a] \arctan[-\text{Sign}[a] y, x] - y \log\left(\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2}\right) \right). \quad (29)$$

Therefore, by considering the correspondence between magnetization and Amperian currents, the magnetic device is shown to be equivalent to a current of $I = -M t$ circulating on the edges of the lamella.

4.2. Corrector or sorter 2

As a result of the projection feature of the phase object approximation, any periodic structure is able to give, in vacuum, the phase shift required by the corrector, or sorter 2, element of the ideal sorter. We consider, as an illustrative example, a periodic array of alternating magnetic stripe domains of width w , aligned along y , in a thin specimen lying in the half-plane $x < 0$. The phase shift introduced by such an array (Fig. 5) has been calculated in analytical form previously [31] and is given by the expression

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{N}{2\pi} \Re \left(2e^{\frac{i\pi y}{w}} H(-x) \Phi \left(e^{\frac{2i\pi y}{w}}, 2, \frac{1}{2} \right) - \text{Sign}(-x) e^{-\frac{\pi(|-x|-iy)}{w}} \Phi \left(e^{-\frac{2\pi(|-x|-iy)}{w}}, 2, \frac{1}{2} \right) \right), \quad (30)$$

where N is the number of flux quanta trapped in the domain, $H(x)$ is the Heaviside step function and $\Phi(z, s, a)$ is the Lerch transcendent function [32]. The phase shift of a basic period of this structure is shown in Fig. 5(a) for $N = 20$, illustrating the triangular shape of the phase in the specimen corresponding to the case of zero-width magnetic domain walls. The slow decrease in phase in the vacuum region is visualized more clearly in the form of a contour map in Fig. 5(b), from which the internal phase contribution has been removed.

The leading Fourier term in the former expression

$$\varphi(x, y) = \frac{4 N}{\pi} \exp\left(-\pi \frac{x}{w}\right) \cos\left(\pi \frac{y}{w}\right) \quad (31)$$

has the analytical form required for sorter 2, as described in Eq. 4.

5. Design of a realistic sorter

In our former paper on an electrostatic sorter [21], we recognized that the use of a line charge of finite length for sorter 1, combined with the need to have a mirror line for neutrality purposes, was responsible for an astigmatic contribution to the phase shift, which could wash out the sorting effect completely. We were able to compensate for this astigmatic contribution by adding two additional line charges (and their images) perpendicular to the line charge, thereby restoring the performance of the device. As magnetic elements do not, in general, require compensating mirror images, a simpler structure comprising only three elements (sorter 1 and two perpendicularly aligned elements) was investigated here. The results were disappointing, indicating that the mirror charges were also required for compensation.

In order to better appreciate the influence of astigmatism and its correction, we first consider a single magnetic element of length $a = 80 \mu\text{m}$ (with the tip at the origin of the coordinate system), acting as a sorter 1 in a device in which a length of the transformed beam of $d = 10 \mu\text{m}$ over a focal length $f = 0.5 \text{ m}$ is required. These values are similar to the conditions used for our last experiments performed for an electrostatic sorter [22]. We are interested in a field of view of $30 \mu\text{m} \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ centred on the tip.

As an illuminating beam, we consider a petal beam [19], which is defined by the equations

$$\psi_{ill} = \mathcal{N}\{\exp[i\ell \arctan(x, y)] + \exp[-i\ell \arctan(x, y)]\} \quad \text{for } x^2 + y^2 < w^2 \quad (32)$$

$$\psi_{ill} = 0 \quad \text{for } x^2 + y^2 > w^2, \quad (33)$$

where \mathcal{N} is a normalization constant.

Figure 7 (a) shows the intensity distribution of the beam, with $w = 10 \mu\text{m}$ and $\ell = 2$, in the sorter 1 plane, over a field of view of $30 \mu\text{m} \times 30 \mu\text{m}$. An amplitude function introduced to take into account the finite dimension of the device is also shown. The intensity before the sorter 2 plane is shown in Fig. 7 (b). Four intensity minima are visible, corresponding to $\ell = \pm 2$. However, there is also a distortion caused by the finite dimensions of sorter 1. A Fraunhofer image calculated for a focal length $F = 2 \text{ m}$ in Fig. 7 (c) shows that the astigmatism blurs the sorting effect completely.

In order to optimize the device without resorting to a replica of the electrostatic device, we introduced two additional magnetic elements at a distance of $40 \mu\text{m}$, with their tips aligned with sorter 1. We then investigated the effect of rotating them with respect to sorter 1, as shown in Fig. 6. For two triangular elements that have lengths of $80 \mu\text{m}$, compensation is achieved at an angle of 10° , as shown in Fig. 8(a). The focal length of the Fraunhofer lens has been increased to $F = 5 \text{ m}$, in order to emphasize the variations and features of the intensity distribution in the diffraction image. Deterioration of the image at 0 and 20° is shown in Fig. 8(b) and Fig. 8(c), respectively. We also tested the effect of placing the return vertical current at a greater distance and of having a trapezoidal instead of a triangular current circuit, but this modification was not as beneficial as the angular compensation.

We compared the results of Eq. 16 numerically with our previous experimental results for electrostatic sorter 1, where the average tilt of the beam was $\frac{d}{f} = 20 \mu\text{rad}$ [22]. A similar result could be obtained for a current of 67 mA . Such a current requires detailed engineering, but is compatible with MEMS technology. For sorter 2 fabricated in the form of either a square wave or a sinusoidal current distribution, we estimate that the typical phase that is obtained by applying a 4 V bias to electrostatic sorter 2 corresponds to $I = 10.7 \text{ mA}$ and $L = 40 \mu\text{m}$.

6. Conclusions

We have described an analogy between magnetic and electrostatic phase elements, which has general importance for fabricating customized phase elements, but is particularly relevant for the present case of an orbital angular momentum sorter. We have used analytical models to derive the shape of the current distribution that is required to achieve a completely magnetic version of the sorter. For the first sorting element, a new design with no direct analogue to the electrostatic case has been introduced to control the astigmatism that is introduced by the device. Numerical calculations indicate that phase shifts analogous to the electrostatic case can be obtained with currents that are within experimentally achievable ranges. The proposed devices have the important advantage that the field sources can be controlled directly, in contrast to the electrostatic case, for which the effective charge could only be controlled through the appropriate shaping of electrodes and by neglecting mutual induction of the elements. The new approach promises to provide a more accurate way to produce near-ideal OAM sorting over a large range of beam sizes.

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Figure 1: Current circuit and corresponding phase shift for a magnetic sorter 1 element. The current closes just behind the element. See text for details.

Figure 2: Square wave current distribution suitable for the sorter 2 element. a) Three-dimensional structure of the current, with a plane cutting it at half of the total amplitude and showing a contour map of the phase shift introduced by the current distribution. Blue and yellow correspond to opposite signs of the phase shift. b) Cosine phase map calculated for a periodic distribution of vertical currents of opposite sign. See text for details.

Figure 3: Sinusoidal current distribution suitable for the sorter 2 element. The three-dimensional structure of the current is illustrated, with a plane cutting it at half of the total amplitude and showing a contour map of the phase shift introduced by the current distribution. Blue and yellow correspond to opposite signs of the phase shift. See text for details.

Figure 4: Discrete representation of a continuous triangular distribution of elementary magnetic dipoles. The shaded prism represents a volume of integration along z

Figure 5: (a) Three-dimensional representation of the phase shift for a basic period of an infinite array of alternately-oriented stripe domains aligned along the y direction in the half-plane $x < 0$. (b) Corresponding phase contour map in the vacuum region for $x > 0$.

Figure 6: Phase map calculated for sorter 1 with astigmatism correction elements. The currents of the sources are indicated schematically. The typical beam position is indicated by a circle.

Figure 7: (a) Petal beam with an OAM $|l| = 2$ intensity distribution. (b) Beam intensity distribution before the sorter 2 element and after it has interacted with the sorter 1 element. (c) Blurred OAM spectrum obtained without astigmatism compensation/correction.

Figure 8: OAM spectrum obtained using a magnetic sorter with a length of $80 \mu\text{m}$ and with a lateral astigmatism corrector oriented at an angle of: (a) 10° (corresponding to Fig. 6), (b) 0° and (c) 20° .